

A guide to selecting renewable high-performing antibodies for Slit-1 for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Abstract

Slit-1 is a secreted glycoprotein involved in axon guidance and neural migration. Here we have characterized nine Slit-1 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID O75093, *SLIT1*, Slit-1, Slit homolog 1 protein, Multiple EGF-like domains protein 4, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation

Introduction

Slit-1 is a 1,534 amino acid secreted glycoprotein that functions as a ligand for Robo (Roundabout) receptors, regulating cell migration, axon guidance, and neural development and regeneration. It is predominantly expressed in the nervous system, where it plays a key role in repulsive axon guidance and the establishment of neural circuits during development (1).

Here, we characterized nine commercial Slit-1 antibodies, for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation using standardized protocols. Antibody performance was assessed by comparing signal in wild-type (WT) and knockout (KO) cell lines. The resulting data can guide the selection of antibodies best suited to specific research needs, enabling robust biochemical and cellular assessment of the target.

This work is part of a broader collaborative initiative involving academics, funders, and antibody manufacturers, aimed at improving biomedical research reproducibility through the systematic characterization of commercial antibodies against human proteins and open data sharing. Antibodies are provided in-kind by participating manufacturers. The approach involves identifying cell lines with sufficient target expression, generating or sourcing corresponding KO cell lines, and evaluating commercially available antibodies, with a focus on renewable (monoclonal and recombinant) reagents (2). We do not provide explicit antibody recommendations; rather, the data are presented to enable independent interpretation. Guidance on data interpretation is available via the YCharOS gateway (3) and in Table 5 of this data note.

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from WT and KO cell lines (2). The first step is to identify a cell line expressing sufficient levels of the target protein to generate a measurable signal with antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) to identify cell lines with expression levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), a threshold we have found to be suitable (4). The Jurkat cell line expresses the *SLIT1* transcript at $5.1 \log_2$ TPM+1, and a Jurkat *SLIT1* KO cell line is available at Abcam (Table 1). As seen on DepMap, the Jurkat cell line harbors a mutation (p.R102C) in the *SLIT1* gene that could affect antibody-epitope binding.

A total of nine antibodies were provided by participating manufacturers. One antibody (ab183704) is reported by the manufacturer to recognize both Slit-1 and Slit-2. While Jurkat cells express *SLIT1*, *SLIT2* expression is negligible ($0.03 \log_2$ TPM+1), indicating that signal observed in this model is unlikely to arise from Slit-2.

First, all nine antibodies were tested in western blot. WT and *SLIT1* KO culture medium were collected, concentrated and resolved on SDS-PAGE, transferred to nitrocellulose membranes, and probed in parallel with Slit-1 antibodies (Figure 1).

The ability of antibodies to capture Slit-1 from Jurkat culture medium was assessed by immunoprecipitation, followed by western blot analysis. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE. For detection, ab151724**, a specific Slit-1 antibody identified in Figure 1 was used (Figure 2).

Although our consensus workflows include immunofluorescence screening, this application was not performed for Slit-1, as it is a secreted protein and is expected to produce low signal-to-noise under standard conditions.

In summary, we screened nine Slit-1 commercial antibodies in western blot and immunoprecipitation by comparing signal in WT *SLIT1* KO Jurkat cells. To assist with data interpretation, Table 5 outlines common antibody performance scenarios across applications. High-quality renewable antibodies detecting Slit-1 were identified for each application. Researchers studying Slit-1 in other species are encouraged to consider these results and verify predicted species reactivity with the manufacturer before proceeding.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. First, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all available antibodies against any given targets. While YCharOS partners provide access to the majority of renewable antibodies, some widely used polyclonal antibodies may not be included.

Second, the YCharOS approach is protein-agnostic and aims to provide objective data on antibody performance without predefined expectations regarding molecular weight or localization. As such, only a brief overview of the protein target is provided, and expert interpretation of banding patterns is encouraged.

Third, experiments are not performed in biological replicates due to the parallel testing of multiple antibodies recognizing distinct epitopes. The identification of at least one specific antibody supports target expression in WT cells and its absence in KO cells, providing a reference for evaluating other antibodies. Experiments are performed using standardized conditions and master mixes to minimize variability. Experiments may be repeated when no signal is detected. Furthermore, these data are generated independently of manufacturers' validation processes, effectively constituting an external replication.

Finally, conclusions are limited to the experimental conditions and cell line used. The reliance on a single cell type represents a constraint, as protein expression levels can influence antibody performance. The use of cancer cell lines also introduces potential confounders, including mutations that may affect antibody-epitope binding. These limitations are inherent to cell line-based validation approaches.

Method

The standardized protocols used for this antibody characterization study were established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers, and antibody manufacturers (1). Brief descriptions of the experimental procedures used in this study are described below.

Cell lines

Cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. To facilitate unambiguous identification and proper citation, all resources are referenced using their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (5, 6).

Primary and secondary antibodies

The primary antibodies are listed in Table 2 and referenced with their RRIDs. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. The used antibody dilutions in western blot are listed in Table 3. In western blot, dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier and titrated when needed. A standardized 2 µg of antibody is tested in immunoprecipitation. Volumes corresponding to 2 µg of each antibody are listed in Table 3. Secondary antibodies and their corresponding concentrations are listed in Table 4.

Antibody screening by western blot

Jurkat WT and *SLIT1* KO cells were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~36 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x *g* to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x *g* to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were then concentrated by centrifuging at 4000 x *g* for 30min using the Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were finally supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340) and 15 µg of protein aliquots were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Protein separation was performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot.

Membranes were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated with the membrane in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated

with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 87788 in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (rabbit antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Culture medium from Jurkat WT was collected as described in the western section above. 0.28 mL aliquots of culture medium at 0.7 mg/mL (0.2 mg of protein) were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 mL of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Data availability

Underlying data

Dataset for the Slit-1 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	TIB-152	CVCL_0367	Jurkat	WT
Abcam	ab326615	CVCL_F4CA	Jurkat	<i>SLIT1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Slit-1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab151724**	1094105-1	AB_3233479	recombinant mono	EP5797(2)	rabbit	1.95	Wb
Abcam	ab183704**	1092869-1	AB_3160160	recombinant mono	EP5796(N)	rabbit	1.02	Wb
GeneTex	GTX134122	43243	AB_2887222	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.81	Wb, IF
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010278-013	3	AB_3741700	recombinant mono	IPI-Slit1.11	rabbit	0.50	IP
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010279-013	3	AB_3741701	recombinant mono	IPI-Slit1.12	rabbit	0.50	IP
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010288-013	3	AB_3741702	recombinant mono	IPI-Slit1.21	rabbit	0.50	IP
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010307-013	3	AB_3741703	recombinant mono	IPI-Slit1.40	rabbit	0.50	IP
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010310-013	3	AB_3741704	recombinant mono	IPI-Slit1.43	rabbit	0.50	IP
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010315-013	3	AB_3741705	recombinant mono	IPI-Slit1.48	rabbit	0.50	IP

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody

Table 3: Dilutions of Slit-1 antibodies used in western blot and immunoprecipitation

Company	Catalog number	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendor-recommended Wb dilution	Wb dilution used	IP volume (µL, for 2 µg input)
Abcam	ab151724**	1.95	1/1000 - 1/10000	1/1000	1.0
Abcam	ab183704**	1.02	1/1000 - 1/2000	1/1000	2.0
GeneTex	GTX134122	0.81	1/500 - 1/3000	1/500	2.5
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010278-013	0.50	-	1/1000	4.0
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010279-013	0.50	-	1/1000	4.0
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010288-013	0.50	-	1/1000	4.0
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010307-013	0.50	-	1/1000	4.0
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010310-013	0.50	-	1/1000	4.0
Institute for Protein Innovation (IPI)	TAB0010315-013	0.50	-	1/1000	4.0

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot and immunoprecipitation

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 (4)

Figure 1: Slit-1 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

Figure 2: Slit-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Slit-1 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium.

Culture media collected from Jurkat WT and *SLIT1* KO were analyzed in western blot with the indicated Slit-1 antibodies. Ponceau-stained membranes are shown to confirm equal loading and efficient protein transfer from gel to membrane. Predicted band size: 167.9 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: Slit-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium.

Immunoprecipitation was performed with culture medium collected from Jurkat WT and using the indicated Slit-1 antibodies. Immunoprecipitates were analyzed by western blot using the Slit-1 antibody ab151724** (1/500). Ponceau-stained membranes are shown. SM=10% starting material; UB=10% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody.